

How to “Do” PIDs and Reap the Benefits: Stakeholder Actions

To derive the full benefits of persistent identifiers, including the interoperability and data flow they enable, all players in the Canadian research ecosystem will need to take action.

INDIVIDUALS (RESEARCHERS, FACULTY, GRAD STUDENTS, AUTHORS)

1. Obtain an ORCID iD and manage your profile.
2. Use your ORCID iD whenever any submission system allows you to.
3. Register for automated ORCID iD updating.
4. Commit to ensuring all your publications get DOIs.
5. Input your institution’s ROR when asked to cite institutional affiliation.

INSTITUTIONS (INCLUDING THE RESEARCH OFFICE AND THE LIBRARY)

1. Get familiar with PIDs and the Canadian PID strategy.
2. Join ORCID-CA and DataCite Canada.
3. Form a cross-institutional PID group to fully leverage local PID benefits.
4. Encourage researchers to obtain ORCID iDs. Provide guidance for how to do so. Actively promote uptake and use. Address reservations and counter reluctance.
5. Implement PID features and plugins – e.g., *Open Journal Systems* has ORCID, DataCite, CrossRef and ROR plugins; *DSpace 7* has built-in ORCID and DOI features, etc.
6. Integrate ORCID iDs into local systems – configure existing integrations or build custom.
7. Offer a DOI minting service or recommend use of *DataCite Fabrica*.
8. Advocate with vendors to improve PID integrations as necessary.
9. Curate and use your institutional ROR in journal publishing systems, data repositories, funder and grant management platforms, and other research systems.
10. Use three PIDs (ORCID, DOIs, and RORs) to normalize data, improving key metadata fields’ quality, consistency and disambiguation in your systems.

FUNDERS OF RESEARCH

1. Integrate ORCID, DOI and ROR in grants management systems.
2. Request or require an ORCID iD from all named investigators.
3. Reduce applicants’ admin burden by collecting DOIs and/or linking to their ORCID profiles, to ensure easy collection of affiliation, funding, and output metadata.
4. Standardize and register Grant IDs (a specific type of DOI) for all funding.
5. In the future, when RAiD becomes available in Canada, ensure their collection.

PUBLISHERS OF RESEARCH

1. Require an ORCID iD for all submitting authors.
2. Enable the capture of RORs and RAiDs too (if applicable/available).
3. Ensure every article, publication, or accompanying dataset is assigned a DOI.

PUBLISHING INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS

1. Enable ORCID, DOI, and ROR functionality, integration and interoperability.
2. Interoperate those so appropriate integrations and resultant benefits occur.

Canadian Research
Knowledge Network

Réseau canadien
de documentation
pour la recherche

Digital Research
Alliance of Canada

Alliance de recherche
numérique du Canada

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